

PHYSICS AND MATHEMATICS

THE APPLICATION OF ORDINARY DIFFERENTIAL EQUATIONS IN MATHEMATICAL MODELLING

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Abstract

As an important branch of mathematics, ordinary differential equations have a wide range of applications in many fields. We are able to analyse and predict practical problems in depth by constructing appropriate models of ordinary differential equations. This paper demonstrates the application of ordinary differential equations in mathematical modelling by constructing mathematical models for practical problems in particle motion, concentration problems, economic and financial forecasting, and so on.

Keywords: ordinary differential equations, mathematical modelling, mathematical model, application.

Ordinary differential equations have a wide range of applications in natural phenomena, engineering problems, control systems, economics and finance, ecosystems, complex networks, biomedicine and computer-aided design. In solving practical problems in these fields, the use of ordinary differential equations to establish mathematical models is a very effective mathematical means, because many problems in the mathematical process, often can not be directly derived from the relationship between the various quantities of the formula, but with the help of ordinary differential equations to find to meet the laws of the function. Ordinary differential equations can combine the theory of mathematics with practice, providing us with effective tools for analysis and prediction.

1 particle motion

The particle motion is one of the most fundamental forms of motion in physics. By means of ordinary differential equations, we can accurately describe the changes in the position, velocity and acceleration of a particle with respect to time. For example, by means of ordinary differential equations constructed from Newton's second law $F = ma$, we can analyse the trajectory and change in velocity of a particle when it is subjected to an external force. This description is important for the study of planetary motion, the free-fall motion of a body in a gravitational field, and so on.

1.1 Formulation of the problem

On the ground with initial velocity v_0 lead upward launch a mass of m objects, assuming that the Earth's gravity and the object to the centre of the Earth distance squared inversely proportional to the neglect of air resistance, try to find the maximum height of the object to reach.

1.2 Modelling

Let the radius of the earth is R , the height of the object rising at the moment t is $s(t)$, according to Newton's law of gravity can be known, the object by the earth's gravitational force is

$$F = -\frac{k}{(R+s)^2} \quad (k > 0), \text{ where } k \text{ is the scaling}$$

factor.

Because when the object is on the ground, $s = 0, F = -mg$, i.e.

$$-mg = -\frac{k}{R^2},$$

so

$$k = mgR^2,$$

therefore

$$F = -mg \frac{R^2}{(R+s)^2},$$

and because the object satisfies Newton's second law during ascent

$$F = ma = m \frac{d^2s}{dt^2},$$

consequently

$$-mg \frac{R^2}{(R+s)^2} = m \frac{d^2s}{dt^2},$$

the sorted ordinary differential equation model is shown in equation (1):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = -\frac{gR^2}{(R+s)^2} \\ s(0) = 0, s'(0) = v(0) = v_0 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

1.3 Model solution

Let $\frac{ds}{dt} = v$, then

$$\frac{d^2s}{dt^2} = \frac{dv}{dt} = \frac{dv}{ds} \cdot \frac{ds}{dt} = v \frac{dv}{ds}, \quad (2)$$

substituting equation (2) into equation (1), we have

$$v \frac{dv}{ds} = -\frac{gR^2}{(R+s)^2},$$

separating the variables gives

$$v dv = -\frac{gR^2}{(R+s)^2} ds,$$

integral can be obtained

$$\frac{1}{2} v^2 = \frac{gR^2}{R+s} + C.$$

Substituting the initial condition $s(0) = 0, v(0) = v_0$, we obtain

$$C = \frac{1}{2} v_0^2 - gR,$$

so

$$\frac{1}{2} v^2 = \frac{gR^2}{R+s} + \frac{1}{2} v_0^2 - gR.$$

As the object reaches its maximum height, $v = 0$, therefore

$$\frac{gR^2}{R+s} + \frac{1}{2} v_0^2 - gR = 0, \quad (3)$$

from equation (3), the maximum height of the object is solved as

$$s_{\max} = \frac{v_0^2 R}{2gR - v_0^2}.$$

2 Concentration issue

Concentration problems are widespread in many fields such as chemistry, biology, and the environment. Such problems usually involve processes such as diffusion and reaction of substances in a certain medium, which are often accompanied by changes in concentration. In order to accurately describe and predict these changes, we can model them using ordinary differential equations. By means of ordinary differential equations, we can establish the concentration of a substance as a function of time and thus analyse the dynamic behaviour of the concentration.

2.1 Formulation of the problem

A swimming pool is about to open, in order to make the pool water to meet the health requirements and does not affect the normal opening, the need for artificial cleaning of the pool water, that is, the discharge of some turbid pool water, while injecting the same amount of clean water. Assuming that the pool is 50 metres long, 30 metres wide, the average depth of 1.2 metres,

At a turbidity of 0.0012 kg/m^3 , the pool water is drained at a rate of $v \text{ m}^3/\text{min}$. Try to develop a mathematical model for the purification of the pool

water. If the turbidity is to be reduced to 0.0006 kg/m^3 in 2 hours, find the rate of drainage v .

2.2 Modelling

Let $x(t)$ denote the mass of the turbidity in the pool water at time t . Take any period of time $[t, t + \Delta t]$, then the change in the mass of the turbidity in the pool water at that time is

$$x(t + \Delta t) - x(t) \approx 0 \cdot v \cdot \Delta t - \frac{x(t)}{1800} \cdot v \cdot \Delta t,$$

Divide both sides equally by Δt , and let $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ to obtain the model of the ordinary differential equation as shown in Eq. (4):

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = -\frac{v}{1800} x(t) \\ x(0) = 2.16 \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

2.3 Model solution

Separating the variables and integrating over Eq. (4) yields

$$x(t) = 2.16 e^{-\frac{v}{1800} t}.$$

When

$$t = 120 \text{ min},$$

$$x(120) = 2.16 e^{-\frac{v}{1800} \cdot 120} = 1800 \cdot 0.0006,$$

solve for

$$v = 15 \ln 2.$$

3 Economic and financial forecasts

The application of ordinary differential equations in the economic and financial fields is extensive and in-depth, which provides us with a powerful mathematical tool to analyse and predict the changing law of economic and financial phenomena, for example, the economic growth model, the model of money supply and demand, etc. can be described by differential equations. By analysing and solving these models, we can predict the development trend of the economy, the supply and demand of money, etc., which provides theoretical support for policy making and investment decisions.

3.1 Formulation of the problem

Economists and sociologists have been concerned with the problem of sales of a new product when it is introduced into the market. Try to develop a mathematical model to describe the sales of a product as a function of time.

3.2 Model assumption

(1) Let the total number of products sold at time t be $x(t)$ and assume $x(t)$ be a continuous function.

(2) Because of their ease of use, products already in use actually act as promotional items, attracting customers who have not yet purchased them. Assume each product attracts an average of k customers per unit of time.

(3) It is known that at time $t = 0$, the number of products sold is x_0 .

3.3 Modelling and solution

By assumption, the ordinary differential equation that $x(t)$ should satisfy is

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = kx \\ x(0) = x_0 \end{cases},$$

solve for

$$x(t) = x_0 e^{kt}. \quad (5)$$

In equation (5) if we let $t \rightarrow +\infty$, it follows that $x(t) \rightarrow +\infty$. This is not true, and in fact $x(t)$ is upper bounded. To overcome the shortcomings of the above model, we make the following improvements:

Assume there be an upper bound on the quantity demanded and denote this upper bound as N , the number of people who have not yet used it (potential customers) is $N - x$. Since the rate of sale of a product is directly proportional to the number of potential customers, noting the proportionality coefficient as k , the ordinary differential equation satisfied by $x(t)$ is:

$$\begin{cases} \frac{dx}{dt} = kx(N - x) \\ x(0) = x_0 \end{cases},$$

solve for

$$x(t) = \frac{N}{1 + \left(\frac{N}{x_0} - 1\right)e^{-Nkt}}.$$

The organic combination of ordinary differential equations and mathematical modelling cleverly combines mathematical theory with practical problems, which can make ordinary differential equations play a greater role in practical applications. With the continuous development of science and technology, the application prospect of ordinary differential equations will be broader.

References

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